

generally does not kill fungi present inside glumes. Although treating seeds with hot water is effective against internal pathogens, the process is precise and difficult for farmers to adopt.

Infected seeds weigh less than healthy and fully filled grains; so mechanical separation based on specific gravity would help differentiate healthy and diseased seeds.

In a field experiment during the punja season (Oct-Jan) at the Moncompu RRS, seeds of Bharathy (highly susceptible to sheath rot) were treated with different concentrations of common salt. Seeds that sank to the bottom in each solution were washed in three changes of clean water and broadcast.

Both sheath blight and sheath rot were reduced as salt concentration increased (see table). In general, sheath blight incidence was low but sheath rot disease was moderate up to 7.5% concentration of the salt solution. Reduction in sheath rot at a

Intensity of sheath blight and sheath rot diseases in seeds treated with different concentrations of salt solution. Kerala, India.

Concn (%) of salt solution	Sheath blight score ^a	Sheath rot score ^b
0.0 (untreated control)	1.8	3.6
2.5	1.5	3.6
5.0	0.6	3.1
1.5	0.4	3.1
10.0	0.2	2.6
12.5	0.1	1.4
15.0	0.3	0.9
17.5	0.2	0.3
20.0	0.2	0.1
C.D.	0.8	1.0

^a1976 Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES) scale: 1 = lesions limited to lower 1/4 of leaf sheaths, 9 = lesions reaching top of tillers; severe infection on all leaves. ^b1976 SES scale: 1 = less than 1% [of tillers affected] (= to resistant check), 9 = 50-100% (= to susceptible check).

concentration of 15% was significant compared to that at lower concentrations.

Mechanical separation of seeds by the method used in this experiment is cheap and simple, and can easily be used by farmers. ■

Transmission of *Rhynchosporium oryzae* Hashioka and Yokogi by seed

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The transmission of *Rhynchosporium oryzae*, the pathogen for rice leaf scald, was investigated in three separate trials. In the first, the fungus was detected by the standard blotter method in seeds of Cheena I collected from a heavily infected farmer's field. The seeds were examined periodically for the presence of the fungus. In the second test, surface-sterilized seeds of Cheena I were rolled in actively sporulating culture of the fungus and were sown in sterilized potted field soils. In another test, seeds from severely infected plants of Cheena I and IET2914 were similarly sown in sterilized field soil. Observations on the appearance of the disease on the seedlings raised in the two tests were recorded until the plants reached maturity.

Isolation of *Rhynchosporium oryzae* from rice seeds of cultivar Cheena I. West Bengal, India.

Date of observation ^a	Seeds(%) giving the fungus	
	Unsterilized	Sterilized
1 Aug 1977	1.14	0
20 Aug	1.13	0
1 Sep	0.86	0
1 Oct	0.61	0
1 Nov	0.00	0
18 Nov	0.00	0

^aSeeds were collected on 26 July 1977.

With the blotter method, the leaf scald fungus could be detected from seed samples of cultivar Cheena I within the first 3 months of collection (see table). The percentage of fungal isolations gradually declined with time of storage. Low percentages of seeds (0.61-1.14%) yielded the fungus. Success in isolating the fungus from unsterilized seed samples and failure to do so from surface-sterilized seeds indicated that the pathogen was externally seedborne.

The plants raised from seeds artificially inoculated with the fungus and from seeds harvested from scald-infected, plants of both Cheena I and IET2914 remained disease free until maturity.

Although a low percentage of rice seeds may have borne the leaf scald fungus *R. oryzae*, the exact role of this seedborne infection in causing the disease could not be established. ■

Studies on sheath rot of rice

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Sheath rot of rice caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) Gams and Hawkeworth has recently become serious in northern India.

A partially selective medium for the fungus has been developed by incorporating 100 ppm Dithane 2-78 and 750 ppm Dicrystin S in Kirchoffs medium. The infected leaf sheaths and grains from diseased panicles were stored at room temperature (8-40° C) and under field conditions to study the survival of the pathogen. The fungus was isolated periodically from diseased parts on Kirchoffs medium. The fungus survived as long as 4 months in seed and 7 months in leaf sheath kept at room conditions and as long as 10 months in leaf sheaths in the field.

The disease development and the meteorological factors for the corresponding period were compared for 3 consecutive seasons from 1976-78 kharif to determine the most favorable conditions. Disease development was maximum when the minimum temperature was 17-20° C and the minimum relative humidity, 40-50% at flowering. The maximum temperature, maximum relative humidity, rainfall, and sunshine could not be correlated with disease severity.

Of the inoculation methods tried, injection of the spore suspension and placement of the pathogen grown on pearl millet inside the boot leaf sheath 7-4 days before flowering gave maximum disease in the field.

Five varieties — Basmati 370, Chinsurah Boro II, Hom Thong, Sigadis,